

Deductive Defense: Proving a Circumstantial God to a Direct Evidence World

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*The ideas expressed in this research paper represent the opinions of the author.

Abstract:

This qualitative analysis of existing literature demonstrates that the case for God, while largely circumstantial, is nonetheless compelling. Although the atheistic contention is that God is not real, this claim is disputed by a series of evidentiary truths that when taken as a whole demonstrate the reality of His existence. For one, the fine tuning of the Earth right down to the exact measurements and proportions needed for life to exist and thrive is no coincidence. Additionally, abiogenesis or life arising from nonliving material by random chance has been mathematically proven impossible. This impossibility means that by deduction, the only way life could have come to be is by way of a living being. In fact, the law of causality leads to the eternal first cause, a spiritual life form that transcends all natural laws. Moreover, even today, there are miracles occurring that defy all natural laws and could not happen without the presence of an omnipotent God. Strengthening the case for God is the testimony of former atheists whose reasoning for conversion contained the same theme, science and reason alone tell only part of the story. Despite their having deep, scientific knowledge, these ex-atheists felt instinctively that something was missing until they found God. Finally, a large-scale study revealed the admissions of a group of scientists in the Biology discipline to the use of questionable research practices for the purpose of making the data say what they wanted it to say. Taken as a whole, this body of evidence makes it clear that God is real.

Introduction

Peter Kreeft once made the statement that “[One] cannot avoid reasoning; [one] can only avoid doing it well.” By this, Kreeft was saying that everyone applies logic; some people however reach incorrect conclusions through the improper application thereof. Similarly, many are convinced that God is not real due to a lack of direct evidence. Reasoning in this manner is flawed as circumstantial evidence, which proves truth by way of inference, is just as valid and in some cases more compelling.

While the case for God is largely circumstantial, a careful analysis of the facts proves without doubt that God is real. These proofs, when taken as a whole, make an irrefutable case for an omnipotent God. Firstly, the fine tuning of the earth is so precise that even one of several aspects being slightly different would render life impossible. Additionally, mathematics by way of the Theoretical Probability Model proves that life arising from nonlife, known as abiogenesis, is impossible; meaning that life can only come from a living source. Due to this impossibility, the first cause, which set life in motion, would have to be a living being. Furthermore, modern day miracles that defy all natural laws represent a circumstantial case for the reality of God.

While these things alone could make the case for God, there is also philosophical evidence, which makes the case stronger. The primary philosophical evidence is the subjective experiences of former atheists who have converted to belief in God based on the similar understanding that science and reason alone cannot explain intangible elements of the human experience. Moreover, the philosophical concept of truth makes a case for God. Admissions by biological scientists in a 2018 study, revealed that many of them have admitted to engaging in questionable research practices, weakening the position of the branch of science in which many

atheists put their trust, biology. While many in the atheist community contend that belief in God is irrational, objective examination of the evidence in its totality proves circumstantially that theistic belief is the only rational position.

The Fine Tuning of the Universe

When arguing a circumstantial case, one must present evidence from multiple sources that when taken as a whole, clearly establish the truth of one's position. The first piece of evidence is that the earth is fine tuned for life to flourish. For one, the earth's distance from the sun is crucial for a stable water cycle. Too far away, and most water would freeze; too close and most water would boil (Sarfati, 2000). Moreover, the color of our sun is just right to allow photosynthesis, if it were bluer or redder, for instance, the reaction would not be strong enough to support plant life. Additionally, fine tuning is seen in all the four fundamental forces of nature—the electromagnetic force, gravity, and the strong and weak nuclear forces that affect subatomic particles. If these had slightly different strengths, [physicists] have argued, stars could not have formed (Frankel, 2022). Adding to this is that calculations indicate that if the strong nuclear force, the force that binds protons and neutrons together in an atom, had been stronger or weaker by as little as 5%, life would be impossible (Collins, 1999). Furthermore, if gravity had been stronger or weaker by 1 part in 1040, then life-sustaining stars like the sun could not exist. This would most likely make life impossible.

Although many objections have been raised as to the fine tuning of the universe proving God's existence, what are the chances that all of these things would align so perfectly by random chance? Is it really practical to think that each and every one of these things would fall in place with such precision as to permit and sustain life by mere coincidence? The concept of subjective probability makes it a definite impossibility. Some scientists call it a random, lucky accident.

Others contend that improbable does not mean impossible. However, the chance of all 154 known factors that make the earth exactly right for life forming randomly is 1 in 7.5×10^{336} . This is 7.5 times and 286 exponential powers below what is considered impossible from the statistical standpoint. Taking such an impossibility and applying reason makes it apparent that this level of sophistication in design requires a deliberate and methodical designer. Referral to such a perfectly crafted circumstance as a random improbability is a downplay of its truly miraculous nature. Applying subjective probability to the way in which Earth is put together, it is impossible that it could be random or by chance.

The Impossibility of Abiogenesis or Life Coming About from Nonlife

In addition to the fine tuning of Earth making it hospitable to life, the impossibility of abiogenesis is another piece of the puzzle in proving God's existence. Despite the many "theories" that assert otherwise, life arising from nonlife is impossible, and only living beings can create other living beings (Bergman, 2000; Creager, 2023). In fact, the Theoretical Probability Model proves abiogenesis to be totally impossible. Omerbasic (2021) who is a Professor of Mathematics, calculated the probability of a drop of hemoglobin evolving by random chance at 1 in 10^{1092} . Being that an event is declared impossible from a statistical standpoint at 1 in 10^{50} , it was Omerbasic's contention that if hemoglobin cannot form by random chance, then it is all the more impossible for life to form by random chance.

Extending his contention and concurring was Creager (2023), a biologist by trade, he calculated the chance that life could arise abiogenetically by random chance at impossible based on a bacteria made up of 483 genes. Creager (2023) made the following observation:

"Given the fact that each amino acid is encoded for by three base pairs, a 50 amino acid protein would require 150 base pairs consisting of 4 possible nucleotides resulting in 4^{150}

or 2×10^{90} , possible combinations, this means that the odds against getting any particular protein encoded by the DNA are 1 in 2×10^{90} (150/531,490) or 1 in 5.75×10^{86} . However, you have to do this 438 times resulting in the odds of encoding all of the amino acids being 1 in 5×10^{38000} . When this is combined with the odds of getting all functional proteins to begin with, we get odds of 1 in 5×10^{38000} [multiplied by] 3.6×10^{24550} or 1 in 1.8×10^{62551} [essentially a probability of 1 in infinity]. This shows that the odds of getting just this much are statistically impossible, and it doesn't include further assembly of the various proteins into a functioning system.” (Creager, 2023, Par. 6)

Based on these examples, which are not all inclusive, it is very clear that contrary to what is proposed by some scientists, abiogenesis cannot happen. The only way for life to come about is from another living being. Despite the multiple attempts of these scientists to justify their refusal to accept these calculations, the fact remains that random chance and time are the variables that scientists utilize when referring to the origins of life. Hence, the Theoretical Probability Model is the only appropriate way to determine the possibility of a proposition that one cannot observe. A theoretical probability of 1 in infinity, is as close mathematically as one can get to absolute impossibility without being able to observe an event. Hence, the logical conclusion is that abiogenesis did not and cannot happen.

Everything that Begins to Exist Has a Cause

When considering that 1.) Earth is fine tuned for life to flourish; and 2.) Life cannot arise from nonlife, the next thing to be considered is causal relationships. If life did not arise from nonlife, where did life come from? By simple deductive reasoning, this question is easily answered. Everything that BEGINS to exist has a cause. God, being the supreme life form did not BEGIN to exist. Instead, God has always existed. Therefore, everything that came after God

had a cause. Life exists therefore life has a cause. Life cannot arise from nonliving material, therefore a living being who would have to have existed infinitely must be the first cause of life.

Modern Day Miracles that Defy Natural Laws

Being that Earth is fine tuned with exact, precise measurement for life to flourish, and that the only way for life to be established is through a living being, one can rest assured that God, a being who transcends natural laws, is certainly real. Taken with the fact that everything has a cause, one can deduce that modern day miracles that defy natural laws have a cause as well. Since they are unable to be explained within the confines of the natural laws, the only explanation for them is the divine intervention of God, proving God's reality once more.

One such miracle is the 2014 case of Ruby Graupera-Cassimiro, who was undergoing an emergency cesarean section when complications caused her to die (The Five Modern Miracles, 2019). For 45 minutes, doctors tried to resuscitate her. When they could not, they made the decision to begin calling friends and family to say their final goodbyes. In an event that shocked the medical community, Ruby came back to life for unknown reasons. She reported having had an experience with spiritual beings while she was dead. Multiple factors make this a miracle attributable only to an omnipotent God. For one, after 10 minutes of oxygen deprivation, death is likely (Dolan et al, 2024). Also, after 15 minutes of oxygen deprivation, survival becomes essentially impossible (Transweb, 2010).

Another modern day miracle also took place in 2014 in the case of Grayson Kirby, who was thrown from a demolition derby car. Based on the accounts of medical personnel, it seemed that death was imminent for Kirby.

“The accident left him in a coma. His lungs were crushed and nearly every other bone in his body was broken. His brain also suffered multiple strokes and hemorrhages and his

kidneys were failing. If he did wake up, he would likely—to put it bluntly—be a vegetable. But his family refused to give up and turned to prayer. Thousands of people in the community and beyond kept Kirby in their thoughts and prayers and wore red shirts designed to show support for the injured man. In a final attempt to revive Kirby, doctors hooked him up to a machine typically used for transplant patients, not trauma patients. Whether it was due to divine intervention or medical intervention (or both), it worked. Ten days after the accident, Kirby opened his eyes and mouthed the words, “I love you,” to his father. The doctors couldn’t believe it.” (Schmidt, 2024, p. 17).

With this knowledge, how can the scientific community swear that there is no stronger force working behind the scenes? Is it then impossible that a spiritual life form, which transcends natural laws, acted intentionally and deliberately? It certainly is not. Could it be that there is power in prayer to an omnipotent God? Doctors cannot explain how Graupera-Cassimiro came back to life after 45 minutes of oxygen deprivation to the brain. Even the best professional doctors are baffled at how Kirby survived an accident that was so extreme that he was placed on a machine used for clinically dead patients to keep their organs healthy enough to be used in a transplant, yet he lived. Miracles like this provide more evidence, which when added to the aggregate of known evidence, makes a case for God.

Former Atheists Who Were Converted

More proof is evident via qualitative evidence in the experiences reported by former atheists who have come to believe in God’s existence. One such case is the case of Mr. Robert Melnichuk, a former atheist, who very clearly felt like science alone was incomplete in its explanation of life, and decided to investigate the Bible. Upon completing his examination, he became intrigued by the fact that there were elements of eyewitness testimony that he saw daily

in his career as a homicide investigator. Using his investigational skills, he was able to determine that the events of the Bible were fact and not as he termed it initially “moralistic mythology.” (Atheism: Why I Converted to Christianity, 2013)” Melnichuk further concluded that there were properties of the Gospels, which very closely resembled the eyewitness accounts of an event witnessed by multiple individuals, which gives more credence to their accuracy. As Mr. Melnichuk examined more closely the properties of the gospels, he launched an all out investigation using both history and the gospels and that was ultimately how he came to faith. By applying known investigative techniques to the scriptures, he discovered that what appeared to be mythology at first glance was actually provable and true, not just in terms of the tangible but the intangible.

Another example is the case of Mrs. Jennifer Fulweiler, who reported being born into an atheist family and not even believing in God as a child. Throughout her life, she describes her experience as a diet of reason and belief in what was provable and observable. (Atheist to Christian Testimony, 2014) When she began studying the scriptures and other world religions, she was not completely persuaded, and decided to put out every hard question on a blog. As stated by Fulweiler (2014)”Christians and atheists had the scientific concepts correct, yet the Christian responses more accurately portrayed the human experience.” As a result, she became compelled to believe in the truth of the scriptures although they were counterintuitive to her. In this case the theme once more is that science explains very well the way the world works. However, there is more than simply the tangible with respect to the human experience. In fact, it was the intangible elements that made the most compelling case. In her own words, the love she felt when her baby was born “had to be more than random chemical reactions.”

Based on these conversions from atheism, the theme that recurred in each case is that despite having scientific knowledge, the participant felt like something was missing intrinsically that could not be described or articulated. It was not until the atheist came to the knowledge of the truth of God's reality that they discovered that only the knowledge of God filled this void. How is it that atheists who never believed in God and thought of the concept of religion as mere wishful thinking would feel like their lives were more fulfilling and complete by accepting God's reality if God weren't real?

Scientists Engaging in Questionable Research Practices (QRPs)

At first glance, many scientific studies are accepted by the public at large, and come across as objective, factual, and logically concrete. Yet, some alarming statistics might cause one to question how much trust should be placed in some of these studies. Frazer & Parker (2018) conducted a study, in which 807 researchers employed in the field of Biology were anonymously interviewed about their research practices and reporting of results. The results of this study call into question the integrity of some in the science community. Adding to the strength of this study is its generalizability being that a minimum sample size to get an accurate picture that represents the population in general is 100 (Bullen, 2024).

“64% of surveyed researchers reported they had at least once failed to report results because they were not statistically significant (cherry picking); 42% had collected more data after inspecting whether results were statistically significant (a form of p hacking) and 51% had reported an unexpected finding as though it had been hypothesized from the start.” (Frazer & Parker, 2018)

This information, which is just one of many studies reported in professional journals, gives the researcher an idea of the types of actions taken by some in the field of biology to

“prove” their case. In essence, to researchers who practice the use of such unethical methodology, the “truth” is their preconceived notions and/or the story they wish to portray. Knowing this begs the question of whether or not one can truly trust the “findings” that are offered in the name of “refuting” God’s existence.

Conclusions

When taken as a whole, the evidence overwhelmingly proves that God is real. The atheist community’s demand for direct evidence does nothing to diminish the probative value of evidence which establishes truth by way of inference. One can liken pieces of circumstantial evidence to blocks; put enough of them together and the tower is built. Regarding the reality of God’s existence, that is exactly what has happened.

One fact that has been very clearly established in support of God’s existence is the fine tuned Earth. Very slight alterations in such aspects as gravity, distance from the sun, the color of the sun, the electromagnetic force, and the strong and weak nuclear forces that affect subatomic particles would render life impossible. Atheists ask us to believe that all of these factors which contain measures that are precise and exact for the sustenance of life are all coincidental. Additionally, the impossibility of life arising from nonlife means by deduction that life had to have originated from a living source.

Since everything except the first cause has a cause, it would be reasonable to infer that the living source previously referenced would be a life source that is imperceptible with the five senses. While atheists would argue that such a life form does not exist, logic refutes that assertion. Can we perceive the mental picture in someone else’s mind? We cannot. Even if the person told us about the mental picture, could we measure the truth of their statement? There is no way we could. Do we believe the mental picture exists? We do. This belief is rooted in a

common experience since we get mental pictures in our own minds. Some may argue that brain waves could tell us about the mental picture. However, the only information that could be obtained in that manner is that the person is thinking, these waves would tell us nothing about the intangible mental picture. The atheist then cannot say that such a life form does not exist simply because they have not experienced the presence thereof. Aren't scientists discovering new life forms all the time that they did not previously believe existed? Could they not one day have an experience with spiritual life as believers have?

With respect to miraculous events, science has no explanation for them. The fact that a woman who was dead and whose brain was deprived of oxygen for 45 minutes came back to life could only have been accomplished by an omnipotent God. And the accident that nearly claimed the life of a young man who was thrown from a derby car caused injuries that have been scientifically proven to make death certain. Yet, he miraculously survived and the scientific community is unable to say why that is because it defies natural laws. How do they know with absolute certainty that a spiritual life form, God, did not act deliberately and intelligently to save him? They do not.

Another circumstantial proof for God is the conversion of former atheists who never in their lives believed previously that God existed. How did they come to the conclusion then that God was real? A recurring theme is that science and reason alone do not explain the human experience. Despite their knowledge of science and how the world works, they knew instinctively that science was not all there was to life. For one former atheist, the birth of her baby showed her that love was more than random chemical reactions. The other ex-atheist found that exploring the scriptures from curiosity helped him uncover the entire picture of life. Can we dismiss their common experience as mere coincidence? How possible is it that people who do

not know one another and have never spoken to each other would reach similar conclusions by random chance? What caused the longing and yearning in these people that said “the scientific is not the entire story?” It is because God is real and capable of reaching out to nonbelievers in ways that are different from what could be quantified or measured.

Finally, the admitted dishonesty of some scientists in the biological science community casts doubt on the scientific claims that many atheists accept as truth without questioning them. This happens because scientists are considered by many to be experts. Hence, they are given a great deal of credibility by virtue of their position. In the study by Frazer & Parker, a great many of these biological scientists admit to abusing this authority by engaging in questionable research practices that call into question the validity of the results. What makes this more unfair is that the biological scientists who are honest and apply the highest standards to their work are impacted by the egregious actions of their colleagues. Can one now determine for sure which biological scientists are being honest and which ones are fabricating, overstating, exaggerating, and eliminating results? It is impossible given this information. Yet from all of the evidence that is known to be true, factual, and established, the only right conclusion is that God is real.

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~ Science and Theology are not mutually exclusive. ~

Biography

An educator and avid lover of science and theology, Dr. Wills is an Independent Researcher, whose love for God fuels his mission to educate the world on the coexistence of science and theology. He has earned a Bachelor of Science (B.S.) in Education; a Master's of Education (M.Ed.); an Educational Specialist Degree (Ed.S.); and a Doctor of Biblical Counseling Degree (D.B.C.).